

1 *Review*

2 **Microwave signal processing over multicore fiber**

3 **Sergi García, David Barrera, Javier Hervás, Salvador Sales and Ivana Gasulla***

4 ITEAM Research Institute, Universitat Politècnica de València, Valencia, 46022, Spain

5 * Correspondence: ivgames@iteam.upv.es

6 Received: 7 November 2017; Accepted: date; Published: date

7 **Abstract:** We review the introduction of the space dimension into fiber-based technologies to
8 implement compact and versatile signal processing solutions for microwave and millimeter wave
9 signals. Built upon multicore fiber links and devices, this approach allows the realization of fiber-
10 distributed signal processing in the context of fiber-wireless communications, providing both
11 radiofrequency access distribution and signal processing in the same fiber medium. We present
12 different space-division multiplexing architectures to implement tunable true time delay lines that
13 can be applied to a variety of microwave photonics functionalities, such as signal filtering, radio
14 beamsteering in phased array antennas or optoelectronic oscillation. In particular, this paper gathers
15 our last work on the following multicore fiber technologies: dispersion-engineered heterogeneous
16 multicore fiber links for distributed tunable true time delay line operation, multicavity devices built
17 upon the selective inscription of gratings in homogenous multicore fibers for compact true time
18 delay line operation, and multicavity optoelectronic oscillation over both homogeneous and
19 heterogeneous multicore fibers.

20 **Keywords:** Microwave photonics; space-division multiplexing; radiofrequency signal processing;
21 multicore fibers; fiber Bragg gratings; optoelectronic oscillators; true time delay lines.
22

23 **1. Introduction**

24 The addition of the spatial dimension to the portfolio of optical multiplexing technologies has
25 been welcomed by the optical communications community as a promising solution to the capacity
26 saturation of conventional singlemode fibers (SMFs), [1]. Space-Division Multiplexing (SDM) aims to
27 increase the transmission capacity over a fixed bandwidth by increasing the number of light paths
28 that are transmitted within the same fiber cladding. Different SDM technologies have been
29 investigated for the last few years including either multicore fibers (MCFs) [2-27], few-mode fibers
30 (FMFs) [28] or a combination of both [29]. In the case of MCFs, we can transmit the multiplex of data
31 signals along the different cores that comprise the fiber while keeping a low level of crosstalk. Most
32 of the research activity on MCF transmission has employed the so-called homogeneous multicore
33 fiber, where N identical cores are confined inside a single cladding with an outer diameter ranging
34 from 125 to 260 μm . The highest capacities demonstrated so far have been realized by means of
35 uncoupled propagation featuring crosstalk values between -72 and -22 dB/100 km, [3]. Here, the use
36 of trench-assisted refractive index profiles plays an important role. Thanks to a better confinement of
37 the optical field, this technique makes the crosstalk insensitive to the fiber bending radius increase,
38 allowing very high capacities as, for instance, the 2.15 Pb/s reached in a 22-core fiber in [26].

39 On the other hand, heterogeneous MCFs were proposed in 2009 to increase the density of cores
40 as compared to homogeneous MCFs. They are composed of non-identical cores characterized by
41 different propagation constants, arranged so that the crosstalk between any pair of neighboring cores
42 is reduced as the phase matching condition is prevented. This crosstalk reduction allows to reduce
43 the core pitch of the fiber and thus increase the number of cores per cross-sectional fiber area. Initial
44 designs of heterogeneous 19-core fibers obtained a core pitch reduction down to 23 μm in a 125- μm
45 cladding diameter by accommodating three different core compositions [9]. Further progress in

46 crosstalk management has incorporated as well trench-assisted heterogeneous configurations, [5,10,
47 20]. This led to larger core multiplicities as, for instance, the 30-core fiber designed with 4 different
48 types of trench-assisted cores in a cladding diameter of 228 μm , [27]; and the recent 37-core fiber
49 fabricated by Sasaki et al. in 2017 using 3 types of trench-assisted cores arranged in a 248- μm cladding
50 diameter, [25]. Recent advances incorporating few-mode transmission in each core have achieved a
51 record spatial channel over 100, for example by combining 36 heterogeneous cores and 3-mode
52 transmission in a 306- μm cladding diameter, [29].

53 In general, with the premise of reducing size, weight, power consumption and cost the field of
54 Microwave Photonics moves towards the integration of the different photonic processing and
55 distribution elements. In this sense, photonic integrated circuits (where processing
56 components/subsystems are integrated in monolithic or hybrid photonic circuits) could be
57 considered as a “vertical integration”, while the use of SDM fiber-distributed technologies could be
58 considered as a “horizontal integration”, that is, integration in a distributed way. The synergy
59 between both disciplines will be key for the future of Microwave Photonics, where SDM fiber
60 technologies will benefit from the implementation of integrated transceivers and interconnection
61 elements. Up to date, research has focused on the implementation of mode
62 multiplexers/demultiplexers for FMF transmission [30,31] and fan-in/fan-out devices for MCF
63 transmission [30,32], including optical MIMO processing [30] as well as MCF switches towards
64 optical add/drop multiplexers, [32]. One of the main challenges here is to couple light from/to an
65 SDM fiber efficiently to/from the facet of a silicon photonic waveguide. Various solutions have been
66 published, including one-dimensional grating couplers arranged in a triangular lattice to match the
67 core distribution of a MCF [30], planar two-dimensional grating couplers driven in anti-phase for
68 mode mux/demux [31], and photonic wire bonding, [33].

69 Despite MCFs were initially envisioned in the context of core and metro optical networks, they
70 can also be applied to a wide range of application fields including radio access networks and multiple
71 antenna connectivity [6,34-35], multi-parameter optical fiber sensing [36] and radiofrequency (RF)
72 signal processing, [37-40]. For instance, Diamandi et al. have recently demonstrated that opto-
73 mechanical intercore crosstalk in MCFs can be very useful for applications such as multicore fiber
74 lasers, parametric amplification in SDM networks for MCFs, sensing or optoelectronic oscillators,
75 [41]. In particular, Microwave Photonics (MWP) signal processing applications, such as microwave
76 signal filtering, beamsteering in phased array antennas and arbitrary waveform generation, can
77 benefit greatly from the use of MCFs in terms of compactness and weight, but also in terms of
78 performance stability and versatility. The current trend in MWP is to dedicate a given fiber-based
79 device or photonic integrated circuit to process the RF signal, while the distribution of the signal is
80 performed by an external optical fiber link. We propose a new MWP approach where we can
81 implement the required signal processing functionalities while we distribute the RF signal to the end
82 user (wireless base station, indoor antenna, radar antenna, etc.). This leads to what we call “fiber-
83 distributed signal processing”, a concept with great potential regarding converged fiber-wireless
84 telecommunications scenarios, as those envisioned for 5G systems and the Internet of Things. A true
85 time delay line (TTDL) can be considered the key building block of radiofrequency signal processing,
86 [37-40,42-50]. This photonic subsystem provides a frequency independent and tunable group delay
87 for the RF signal within a given frequency range. A variety of photonic technology approaches have
88 been reported for the implementation of optical TTDLs over the past 30 years, using either fiber-
89 based systems or photonic integrated circuits. Configurations built upon singlecore SMFs featured
90 operation bandwidths ranging from 0.1 up to 40 GHz and RF delays ranging from 0.4 up to 8 ns.
91 These configurations include the use of switched fiber architectures and dispersive fibers [43], the
92 inscription of different Fiber Bragg Grating (FBG) devices [44-46] as well as the exploitation of
93 nonlinearities such as Stimulated Brillouin Scattering [47]. On the other hand, integrated photonics
94 technologies have demonstrated operation bandwidths from 2 up to 50 GHz and RF delays from 40
95 up to 140 ps. Significant examples include ring cavities in Silicon on Insulator [48], racetrack
96 resonators in Silicon Nitride [48] as well as photonic crystal structures [49] and semiconductor
97 amplifiers [50] based on Indium Phosphide.

98 Figure 1 shows the general idea that underlies the TTDL built upon a multicore fiber. The goal
 99 here is to obtain at the output of the fiber link or device a given set of time-delayed samples of the
 100 modulating RF signal that was injected at the input. This set of replicas must be characterized by a
 101 constant basic differential delay $\Delta\tau$ experienced between adjacent samples. We identify this
 102 configuration as a 1D (1-dimensional) TTDL since all the samples are given by exploiting the spatial
 103 diversity (or core diversity) behavior of the MCF. However, this approach potentially offers not only
 104 1D, but also 2D (2-dimensional) operation if we incorporate the optical wavelength diversity
 105 provided, for instance, by an array of lasers emitting at different optical wavelengths. This very
 106 general idea will adapt properly to the particular type of MCF technology employed. In the case of a
 107 heterogeneous MCF, we can design each core with a different refractive index profile as to provide a
 108 different group delay, [51-53]. In the case of homogeneous MCFs, where all the cores are in principle
 109 identical, we must incorporate dispersive optical elements in each one of the cores, [53].

110

111 **Figure 1.** General concept underlying the sampled true time delay line built upon a multicore fiber

112 We gathered in this paper our latest work on the area of radiofrequency signal processing using
 113 different space-division multiplexing technologies. First, we addressed how to design dispersion-
 114 engineered heterogeneous MCFs to act as distributed and tunable true time delay lines. Then, we
 115 reviewed our work on the fabrication of compact TTDL devices based on the inscription of grating
 116 elements along the cores of a homogeneous MCF. Finally, optoelectronic oscillation is presented as
 117 one of the MWP applications that benefits from the fiber integration offered by SDM.

118 **2. Sampled delay line operation over a heterogeneous MCF link**

119 Most of the research activity in heterogeneous MCFs is focused on high-capacity digital
 120 communications. While keeping equal propagation characteristics (in particular the value of the
 121 chromatic dispersion parameter D) in all the cores is important in digital SDM applications, for the
 122 implementation of tunable TTDLs it is important to have different values at a fixed wavelength.
 123 Therefore, a new procedure for designing heterogeneous MCFs has to be developed where, while
 124 keeping the advantages in terms of crosstalk and immunity to bends, one can have the flexibility of
 125 tailoring the chromatic dispersion parameter of each individual core. With that aim in view, we have
 126 proposed and evaluated 7-sample tunable TTDLs based on different designs of heterogeneous 7-core
 127 fibers, [51-53].

128 The design of heterogeneous MCFs to operate as group-index-variable delay lines implies that
 129 each core features an independent group delay with a linear dependence on the optical wavelength.
 130 The group delay $\tau_{g,n}(\lambda)$ of a particular core n can be expended in its 2nd-order Taylor series' around
 131 an anchor wavelength λ_0 as

$$\tau_{g,n}(\lambda) = \tau_{g,n}(\lambda_0) + D_n \cdot (\lambda - \lambda_0) + 1/2 \cdot S_n \cdot (\lambda - \lambda_0)^2, \quad (1)$$

132 where D_n is the chromatic dispersion and S_n the dispersion slope of core n at λ_0 . For proper TTDL
 133 operability, D_n must increase linearly with the core number n while keeping a linear behavior of the
 134 group delay with the optical wavelength. If we force all cores to share the same group delay value at

135 λ_0 , we can control the basic differential delay between samples, $\tau_{g,n+1}(\lambda) - \tau_{g,n}(\lambda)$, to provide continuous
 136 tunability from 0 up to tens (or even hundreds) of ps/km. This gives us the possibility of
 137 implementing fiber-distributed signal processing links with lengths up to a few kilometers.

138 We must therefore customize the refractive index profile of each single core to provide the
 139 desired spectral delay characteristics. The use of trench-assisted cores improves not only the intercore
 140 crosstalk robustness, but also offers more design versatility since more design parameters are
 141 involved [52]. Figure 2(a) shows the schematic of the trench-assisted step-index refractive index
 142 profile, where a_1 is the core radius, a_2 is the core-to-trench distance, w is the trench width, Δ_1 is the
 143 core-to-cladding relative index difference, and Δ_2 is the cladding-to-trench relative index difference.
 144 By suitable modifications of these parameters, we can obtain the required linearly incremental
 145 chromatic dispersion values and the common group delay at the anchor wavelength. In [53], we
 146 found an optimum TTDL design in terms of both time delay tunability and crosstalk for a 7-core fiber
 147 with trench-assisted step-index core profiles. Figures 2(b-c) represent the computed group delay and
 148 dispersion for each core as a function of the core radius for all the cores. As shown, by properly
 149 adjusting the design parameters at the anchor wavelength $\lambda_0 = 1.55 \mu\text{m}$, we obtain: (1) identical group
 150 delays at λ_0 and (2) a set of dispersion values ranging from 14.75 up to 20.75 ps/(km·nm) with an
 151 incremental dispersion of 1 ps/(km·nm).

152 **Figure 2.** (a) Refractive index profile of the fiber cores; (b) Group delay and (c) chromatic dispersion
 153 of each core as a function of the core radius. Each filled circle represents the selected core radius and
 154 the corresponding group delay and chromatic dispersion values.

155 As required in heterogeneous MCF links, we must assure a low level of intercore crosstalk as
 156 well as robustness against fiber curvatures. At a first stage of the design process, we focused mainly
 157 on reducing the crosstalk, so we aimed to reduce the radius of the cores as to minimize the coupling
 158 coefficient, [3,4]. Apart from the expected intercore crosstalk minimization, we found that the higher-
 159 order dispersion (i.e., the dispersion slope) induces serious detrimental effects that can degrade the
 160 performance of the delay line. Thus, we decided to move to higher core radii while keeping good
 161 crosstalk responses and preserving the linear behavior of the group delay with the optical wavelength
 162 in a wide range. The performance of the delay line in terms of intercore crosstalk and robustness
 163 against curvatures can be controlled by properly adjusting the effective index of the cores. One of the
 164 major detrimental effects that can degrade the performance of heterogeneous MCFs is the crosstalk
 165 dependence on the phase-matching condition between adjacent cores when the fiber is bent, [3-5].
 166 The threshold bending radius, R_{pk} , which is the maximum curvature that can induce a phase matching
 167 between any pair of adjacent cores, can be expressed as, [5],

$$R_{pk} = \Lambda \cdot n_{eff,n} / |n_{eff,n} - n_{eff,m}|, \quad (2)$$

168 where Λ is the core pitch and $n_{eff,n}$ is the effective index of core n . To minimize the threshold bending
 169 radius as much as possible, we designed the core refractive index profiles and placed the cores inside
 170 the fiber cross section as to maximize the difference in the effective indices of adjacent cores Figure
 171 3(a) represents the schematic cross section of the fiber. The core pitch was set to $35 \mu\text{m}$ and the
 172 cladding diameter to $125 \mu\text{m}$. The selected values for the design parameters together with the

173 computed group delays, dispersions and effective indices of each core are summarized in Table 1.
 174 We simulated the worst-case crosstalk versus bending radius for a 10-km MCF link. We see from
 175 Figure 3(b) that the threshold bending radius is located at 103 mm, as expected from Eq. (2), and the
 176 crosstalk level above the phase matching region is kept below -90 dB.

177 **Figure 3.** (a) Schematic cross section of the designed MCF; (b) Computed worst-case crosstalk as a
 178 function of the bending radius, [53].

179 **Table 1.** Core design parameters and computed fiber characteristics of the designed MCF, [49].

Core	a_1	a_2	w	Δ_1 (%)	τ_g (ps/m)	D (ps/(km·nm))	n_{eff}
1	3.42	5.48	3.02	0.3864	4918.543	14.75	1.4534
2	3.60	5.03	2.61	0.3762	4918.543	15.75	1.4535
3	3.62	4.35	3.32	0.3690	4918.543	16.75	1.4534
4	4.26	4.92	4.67	0.3588	4918.543	17.75	1.4539
5	3.49	2.81	5.41	0.3476	4918.543	18.75	1.4529
6	4.79	3.35	3.32	0.3435	4918.543	19.75	1.4540
7	4.98	2.42	4.05	0.3333	4918.543	20.75	1.4540

180

181 The designed 7-core fiber offers a linear and incremental behavior of the group delay of each
 182 core as a function of the optical wavelength in a wide wavelength range, as shown in Figure 4(a).
 183 This allows us to implement tunable TTDLs that can be used as the basic element to perform multiple
 184 MWP applications. As a proof of concept, we evaluated the performance of this delay line when it is
 185 applied to implement typical signal processing tasks, such as microwave signal filtering and radio
 186 beamsteering for phased array antennas. Figure 4(b) shows the computed responses of the
 187 corresponding beamforming (upper part) and filtering (lower part) functionalities for a 10-km link.
 188 This delay line allows us the possibility of continuously tuning the free spectral range (FSR) of the
 189 filter and the antenna beam direction by changing the operation wavelength of the laser. For instance,
 190 we see how changing the operation wavelength from 1560 up to 1575 nm induces a reduction on the
 191 FSR from 10 down to 4 GHz and a variation on the beam direction from 180 down to 90° without any
 192 significant degradation due to higher-order dispersion effects.

193 **Figure 4.** (a) Computed group delay of each core as a function of the optical wavelength for the
 194 designed MCF; (b) Computed array factor as a function of the beam pointing angle (upper part) and
 195 computed transfer function as a function of the RF frequency (lower part) for the 10-km link of the
 196 designed MCF and an operation wavelength of 1560 nm (blue solid lines) and 1575 nm (red dashed
 197 lines).

198 Despite the expected potential of these fibers, we must take into account that their performance
 199 in terms of TTDL operability could be degraded due to inaccuracies in the fabrication process. Since
 200 the fabrication tolerances for MCFs are at the moment in the order of $\pm 0.1 \mu\text{m}$ for the core radius,
 201 important discrepancies on the designed dispersion and group delay values may occur. In particular,
 202 we could expect a variation on the designed values up to several ps/km (~ 10 ps/km) for the group
 203 delay and more than 0.2 ps/km/nm for the dispersion. Actually, the fabrication process would involve
 204 several fabrication and re-design stages to allow the manufacturers to properly optimize the process
 205 with the feedback returned from our evaluations. To minimize possible detrimental effects, we have
 206 obtained a *robust-to-fabrication-tolerances* design that trades part of its delay line potential to overcome
 207 the fabrication discrepancies. Our main strategy here is to avoid the matching point of the group
 208 delays at the anchor wavelength, forcing the group delays at that wavelength $\tau_{g,n}(\lambda_0)$ to follow a
 209 similar incremental law as the dispersion does (see Table 1). With this solution, we expect a maximum
 210 relative error on the delay line performance lower than $\pm 10\%$. Nevertheless, this robustness will lead
 211 to a tradeoff with the frequency tunability of the delay line, so we may expect a reduction on its
 212 tunability to a 10-GHz range, while the original design is expected to cover from a few GHz up to the
 213 mm-wave band.

214 3. Sampled delay line operation over a homogeneous MCF multicavity device

215 Most of the research activity on SDM has employed the so-called homogeneous multicore fiber,
 216 where all the cores are in principle identical and, thus, share the same propagation characteristics,
 217 i.e., the same group delay τ and chromatic dispersion parameter D . The implementation of the
 218 tunable true time delay line that we propose will however require different values of these
 219 parameters at each core. Therefore, a novel approach for designing true time delay lines based on
 220 commercial homogeneous MCFs should be accomplished through the in-line incorporation of
 221 additional dispersive optical elements in each core, while preserving the crosstalk levels. In this case,
 222 one should design a multicavity device where the different cavities are produced by the inscription
 223 of individual FBGs at selective positions along the cores.

224 Optical devices built upon the inscription of FBGs in single-core singlemode fibers have been
 225 widely investigated as dispersive 1D (1-dimensional) sampled delay lines [54], where the use of the
 226 optical wavelength diversity allows the tunability of the basic differential delay $\Delta\tau$. If we incorporate
 227 the spatial or core diversity, we obtain a 2D (2-dimensional) delay line that offers a higher degree of
 228 flexibility, versatility and compactness. Actually, previous work on FBG inscription in MCFs has
 229 focused mainly on the simultaneous writing of the same grating (i.e., placed at the same position) in
 230 all the cores, mainly for sensing and astrophotonics [36,55]. In order to inscribe individual gratings
 231 in a selective way, we developed the first fabrication method to inscribe high-quality gratings located
 232 in arbitrary longitudinal positions along the selected fiber core, [56]. Figure 5 shows the scheme of
 233 the FBG writing setup that is based on the moving phase mask technique. First, the laser beam is
 234 conditioned by a mirror that is mounted in a piezo-electric transducer that can induce a beam vertical
 235 deflection and then by two cylindrical lenses that allow the control of both beam height and width.
 236 The beam width and the distance between the fiber and the phase mask was adjusted in order to
 237 control the interference pattern created after the phase mask. For a phase mask with a period of 1070
 238 nm, the maximum width that allows inscription in a single outer core is approximately 23 μm . On
 239 the other hand, the beam height, which is determined by the size of the cores and their arrangement
 240 in the fiber cross section, was adjusted within the range from 30 to 50 μm .
 241

242

243

Figure 5. General scheme of the FBG inscription setup, [56].

244

245

246

247

248

249

250

251

252

253

254

255

256

257

258

By slightly modifying the above technique, we have fabricated different multicavity TTDL devices, either inscribing the same FBG in groups of cores or in individual cores [56]. Figure 6(a) shows, as an example, the scheme of a multicavity device that is based on the selective inscription of FBGs in three outer cores, identified as 4, 5 and 6. The MCF is a commercial 7-core fiber characterized by a cladding diameter of 125 μm and a core pitch of 35 μm . Each one of these cores comprises an array of three uniform gratings, being each one centered at a different wavelength, that is $\lambda_1 = 1537.07$ nm, $\lambda_2 = 1541.51$ nm and $\lambda_3 = 1546.26$ nm. To assure that the delay line operates in wavelength diversity, we have written the arrays to feature incremental distances between FBGs when going from core to core, i.e., 20-mm, 21-mm and 22-mm distances, respectively, within cores 6, 5 and 4. On the other hand, the spatial or core diversity arises from the incremental displacement between FBGs centered at the same wavelength but inscribed in adjacent cores, i.e., 6-mm, 7-mm and 8-mm displacements, respectively, for the wavelengths λ_1 , λ_2 and λ_3 . As appreciated from the optical spectra in reflection gathered in Figure 6(b), all the FBGs present similar levels of strength with a maximum difference of 3 dB.

259
260
261
262

Figure 6. (a) Schematic of the multicavity device built by selectively inscribing FBGs in three of the outer cores of the commercial homogeneous 7-core fiber; (b) Corresponding measured optical spectrum in reflection, [56].

263
264
265
266
267
268
269
270
271
272
273
274
275
276
277
278
279
280

The performance of this multicavity delay line device was evaluated in the context of microwave signal filtering, [37]. To achieve the filtering effect, we combined and photodetected all the delayed RF signal samples coming from the MCF device output. Figure 7(a) illustrates the experimental setup where we used either an array of three low-linewidth lasers or a broadband optical source followed by a 2-nm-bandwidth filter. Actually, the broadband source is required to avoid coherent interference when we detect together the samples coming from different cores with a differential delay lower than the coherence time of the low-linewidth laser. We see in Figure 7(b) the measured radiofrequency responses for the filters obtained when we operate in wavelength diversity, i.e., gathering the delayed samples coming from a given single core. By changing from core to core (core 4, 5 or 6), we can reconfigure the filter, varying the FSR from 4.45 up to 4.97 GHz. The same device can operate using the spatial diversity provided by the cores if we detect the delayed samples that come from different cores but share to the same wavelength. Figure 7(c) shows the measured responses given by each of the three input optical wavelengths, where the FSR varies from 12.50 up to 17.76 GHz. These experimental results are actually in very good agreement with the theoretical ones, with small discrepancies in the basic differential delays that may be caused by discrepancies between the theoretical and actual values of the core refractive indices and small imbalances in the reflectivity strength of the FBGs.

281
282
283
284

Figure 7. (a) Microwave signal filtering experimental setup; measured radiofrequency responses operating in (b) wavelength diversity (for each one of the radiated cores) and (c) spatial diversity (for each one of the optical wavelengths), [56].

285 4. Multiloop optoelectronic oscillation over a multicore fiber

286
287
288
289
290

Multicavity or multiloop optoelectronic oscillators (OEOs) [57-61] can benefit from a reduction of size and weight if the different cores of a multicore fiber act as the required oscillation cavities. In addition, since all the cavities are hosted within the same cladding, this approach provides a fiber integrated medium for enhancing the OEO relative stability against environmental and mechanical fluctuations. Introduced by Yao and Maleki in 1996, first in a single-cavity configuration [62], OEOs

291 can generate RF signals with a low linewidth in a feedback-loop structure along a broad frequency
 292 range. A high level of spectral purity in OEOs will require a long fiber loop, what translates into a
 293 large number of oscillation modes that are separated by a small frequency period. Therefore, very
 294 selective RF filters will be required to select only a single oscillating mode. In 2000, dual-cavity OEOs
 295 were conceived to alleviate this narrowband RF filter requirement [57]. In essence, a short loop
 296 provides the required spectral separation between adjacent oscillating modes while a long loop is
 297 responsible for the spectral purity. The number of loops can as well be generalized to an arbitrary
 298 number, [58-61,63]. In concrete, the work reported in [58] experimentally demonstrated 3-cavity
 299 OEOs by using three different singlemode fiber links whose lengths were multiple of a given
 300 reference value.

301 The incorporation of MCFs as the hosting medium for all the cavities was first proposed and
 302 theoretically evaluated in [59] considering both homogeneous and heterogeneous fiber
 303 configurations. There, we show how homogeneous MCFs allow for two different OEO architectures,
 304 highly unbalanced dual-cavity operation (the cavity lengths are a multiple of a reference value) and
 305 multi-cavity vernier operation (the cavity lengths are slightly different), where moderate and long
 306 cavity lengths (> 2 m) are compatible with a high-spectral purity and multi-GHz oscillation mode
 307 spectral separation. The experimental demonstration of both multicavity architectures was reported
 308 for the first time in [63] over a 20-m-long commercial homogeneous MCF link. This MCF comprises
 309 7 cores and is characterized by a cladding diameter of 125 μm , a core separation of 35 μm and a core
 310 mode field diameter of 6.4 μm . As an example, we gather here the main experimental results obtained
 311 for a 3-cavity multicavity Vernier optoelectronic oscillator. Figure 8 shows the experimental setup
 312 where 3 cores of the MCF behave as the 3 cavities of the oscillator. For simplicity, we used a 3-m long
 313 external SMF to produce the required incremental delay between cavities to achieve the Vernier
 314 effect, and variable delay lines (VDLs) to adjust finely the length difference between cavities. Once
 315 the signals are photodetected, coupled together and amplified, a 4.4 to 5.0 GHz tunable RF filter with
 316 a 30-MHz bandwidth is used to select the desired oscillation mode.

317

318 **Figure 8.** Setup for the experimental demonstration of a multi-cavity Vernier OEO over a 7-core
 319 homogeneous fiber. PC: polarization controller, RF: radiofrequency, EOM: electro-optic modulator,
 320 VDL: variable delay line, EDFA: Erbium-doped fiber amplifier, VOA: variable optical attenuator, PD:
 321 photodetector. (Blue: optical path. Red: electrical path), [63].

322

323 In general, the oscillation frequencies of a multi-cavity OEO verify $f_o = n_i/\tau_i$, for $n_i = 1, 2, \dots$, ($i =$
 324 $1, 2, \dots, N$), where N is the total number of cavities and τ_i is the time delay experienced in each cavity
 325 i including both the optical and the RF delays. The oscillation frequencies for the Vernier
 326 configuration verify $f_o = n / \Delta\tau$ (for $n = 1, 2, \dots$) where $\Delta\tau$ is the incremental delay between cavities
 327 that produces the Vernier effect, [63]. Figure 9(a) shows the measured RF spectrum for the 3-cavity
 328 Vernier OEO where we matched the oscillating modes of all 3 cavities at the frequency located near
 329 4.494 GHz. For the sake of comparison, we have plotted as well the resulting spectrum for a 2-cavity
 330 Vernier configuration over the same fiber. A 10-dB power reduction is observed at the spurious peaks
 331 corresponding to the minor oscillating modes of the single cavities when going from 2 to 3 loops.
 332 Figure 9(b) gathers three consecutive oscillating modes for the 3-loop configuration featuring a FSR

333 of 61 MHz. We can see that the 30-MHz RF filter bandwidth is then narrow enough to allow single-
 334 mode oscillation for the Vernier configuration. Regarding the frequency stability of the OEO, we
 335 observed that the oscillating mode could be shifted a few kHz due to the lack of proper isolation and,
 336 probably, due to possible fluctuations of the pump current applied to the EDFAs. This could actually
 337 induce non-desired mode-hopping effects. Nevertheless, the short lengths that characterized the fiber
 338 loops contribute to minimize this effect since they result in single-cavity FSRs (when each cavity
 339 operates in isolation) on the order of 2 MHz. Even more important, we observed that this effect was
 340 strongly reduced as we increased the number of cavities from 2 to 3, so we can consider our 3-cavity
 341 Vernier architecture considerably robust against possible mode hopping effects.

342

343

344

Figure 9. Experimental oscillation spectra of a multi-cavity Vernier OEO using a 20-meter 7-core fiber for (a) dual- versus triple-loop operation; (b) 3 consecutive oscillation modes for the triple-loop operation, [63].

345

346

347

348

349

350

351

352

353

Figure 10 shows the measured phase noise spectrum for the 3-cavity Vernier architecture (compared to the 2-cavity Vernier architecture), where we observe a -85 dBc/Hz phase noise level at a 10-KHz offset from the carrier that decreases down to -130 dBc/Hz for a 1-MHz offset. We must note that the phase noise values can be significantly reduced by using low-residual phase noise components, by reducing the optical losses and thus suppressing the need for optical amplifiers, and by increasing the MCF length.

354

355

356

Figure 10. Experimental phase noise spectrum of a multi-cavity OEO using a 20-meter 7-core fiber comparing dual- and triple-loop Vernier configurations, [63].

357

358 In addition, as we proposed for 2D tunable true time delay operation, dispersion-engineered
 359 heterogeneous MCFs can be applied to implement tunable OEO operation. In [59], we introduced
 360 vernier OEO operation built upon heterogeneous MCF links with long-cavity lengths (> 1 km) that
 361 can provide high-spectral purity and multi-GHz oscillation mode spectral separation, while
 362 providing lower phase noise operation. If the dispersion parameter D in each core is a multiple of a
 363 basic value ΔD (incremental dispersion parameter), the oscillation frequency for a core with a length
 364 L is given by [59]:

$$f_o = m / (\tau_{g0} L + \Delta D L \Delta \lambda), \text{ for } m = 1, 2, \dots \quad (2)$$

365 where τ_{g0} is the group delay per unit of length at a given anchor wavelength λ_o and $\Delta \lambda = \lambda - \lambda_o$. A
 366 distinctive feature of this OEO is the possibility of tuning the oscillation frequency by changing $\Delta \lambda$,
 367 in other words, by using a tunable laser. Figure 11 shows this relationship (left) and the oscillation
 368 frequencies (right) in between 10 and 20 GHz, computed for a set of selected values of $\Delta \lambda$.

369

370 **Figure 11.** (Left) Oscillation frequency versus wavelength detuning for a vernier multi-cavity OEO
 371 based on a 7-core heterogeneous fiber for $\tau_{g0} = 5$ ns/m, $D = 1$ ps/km.nm and $L = 5$ km; (Right)
 372 Corresponding oscillation spectrum for the different wavelength detuning positions, [59].

373 5. Conclusions

374 We have reviewed the application of space-division multiplexing optical technologies for
 375 Microwave Photonics signal processing based on the use of both homogeneous and heterogeneous
 376 multicore fibers. In the case of heterogeneous multicore fibers, we showed that the proper design of
 377 the trench-assisted refractive index profile of each core results in length-distributed true time delay
 378 lines (up to a few km) with a linear tunability with the operational optical wavelength. In the case of
 379 homogeneous multicore fibers, the selective incorporation of FBGs placed at different positions along
 380 the individual cores of the fiber allows the implementation of compact delay line devices with a
 381 length lower than 10 cm. We like to name these solutions as fiber-distributed signal processing
 382 elements since they are able to process the signal while it is being distributed, for instance, in the
 383 context of 5G radio access networks. In this framework, multiple functionalities can be accomplished,
 384 including arbitrary waveform generation, reconfigurable signal filtering, optical beamforming
 385 networks for phased array antennas and analogue-to-digital conversion. A particular functionality
 386 that has been gathered in this paper is multicavity optoelectronic oscillations, where the required
 387 optical loops can be provided by the different cores of a single MCF in a variety of configurations.
 388 Future fiber-wireless access networks will benefit from the reported SDM approach in terms of
 389 compactness as compared to a set of parallel singlemode fibers, performance stability against
 390 mechanical or environmental conditions and operation versatility offered by the simultaneous use of
 391 the spatial- and wavelength-diversity domains. Moreover, the synergistic combination of photonic
 392 integrated circuits (understood as a “vertical integration”) and the SDM fiber technologies gathered

393 in this work will contribute to the reduction of size, weight and power consumption that will drive
394 the future of Microwave Photonics.

395 The research work reviewed here opens the way towards the development of parallel fiber-
396 based signal processing systems for microwave and millimeter-wave signals that will be applicable
397 to a myriad of fields including physical, chemical and smart structure sensing, medical imaging,
398 optical coherence tomography, broadband electronic and RF measurement instrumentation. Further
399 research on this topic will be accomplished mainly in the framework of the European Consolidator
400 Grant InnoSpace awarded by the European Research Council. In this sense, we will address among
401 others: (1) the fabrication and subsequent experimental demonstration of dispersion-engineered
402 heterogeneous MCFs for tunable time delay operation; (2) how to scale the number of cores beyond
403 seven in both heterogeneous MCF link solutions and FBG-inscribed MCF devices; (3) the
404 experimental demonstration of OEOs built upon heterogeneous MCFs; (4) the improvement of the
405 phase noise performance in general in MCF-based OEOs; and (5) the consideration of other space-
406 division multiplexing technologies for microwave photonics signal processing.

407

408 **Acknowledgments:** This research was supported by the ERC Consolidator Grant 724663, the Spanish Projects
409 TEC2015-62520-ERC, TEC2014-60378-C2-1-R and TEC2016-80150-R, the Valencian Research Excellency Award
410 Program GVA PROMETEO 2013/012, the Spanish MECDFPU Scholarship (FPU13/04675) for J. Hervás, as the
411 Spanish scholarships MINECO BES-2015-073359 for S. García and the Spanish MINECO Ramon y Cajal program
412 RYC-2014-16247 for I. Gasulla.

413 **Author Contributions:** I.G. conceived the ideas and supervised the work. S.G and I.G worked on the design and
414 evaluation of delay lines based on heterogeneous MCFs. J.H., D.B and S.S. were involved in the fabrication and
415 experimental characterization of delay lines based on the inscription of FBGs in homogeneous MCFs. S.G and
416 I.G. worked on the optoelectronic oscillators. S.G and I.G. performed the manuscript writing.

417

418 References

- 419 1. Richardson, D. J.; Fini, J. M.; Nelson, L. E. Space-division multiplexing in optical fibres. *Nat. Photonics* 2013,
420 7, 354-362.
- 421 2. Puttnam, B. J. et al. 2.15 Pb/s transmission using a 22 core homogeneous single-mode multi-core fiber and
422 wideband optical comb. *41st European Conference on Optical Communications (ECOC) 2015*, Valencia, Spain,
423 postdeadline 1-3.
- 424 3. Koshiha, M. Design aspects of multicore optical fibers for high-capacity long-haul transmission. *Proceedings*
425 *of IEEE 2014 Int. Topical Meeting on Microwave Photonics (IEEE)*, 318-323.
- 426 4. Hayashi, T. et al. Physical interpretation of intercore crosstalk in multicore fiber: effects of macrobend,
427 structure fluctuation and microbend. *Opt. Express* 2013, 21, 5401-5412.
- 428 5. Tu, J. et al. Optimized design method for bend-insensitive heterogeneous trench-assisted multi-core fiber
429 with ultra-low crosstalk and high core density. *J. Lightwave Technol.* 2013, 31, 2590-2598.
- 430 6. Galvé, J. M; Gasulla, I; Sales, S.; Capmany, J. Reconfigurable Radio Access Networks using Multicore
431 Fibers. *IEEE J. of Quantum Electronics* 2016, 52(1), 1-7.
- 432 7. Saitoh, K.; Matsuo, S. Multicore fiber technology. *J. Lightwave Technol.* 2016, 34(1), 55-66.
- 433 8. Matsuo, S. et al. High-spatial-multiplicity multicore fibers for future dense space-division-multiplexing
434 systems. *J. Lightwave Technol.* 2016, 34(6). 1464-1475.
- 435 9. Koshiha, M.; Saitoh, K.; Kokubun, Y. Heterogeneous multi-core fibers: proposal and design principle. *IEICE*
436 *Electron. Express*, 6(2). 98-103.
- 437 10. Tu, J.; Long, K.; Saitoh, K. An efficient core selection method for heterogeneous trench-assisted multi-core
438 fiber. *IEEE Photon. Technol. Letters* 2016, 28(7). 810-813.
- 439 11. Feng, Z. et al. Ultra-high capacity WDM-SDM optical access network with self-homodyne detection
440 downstream and 32QAM-FBMC upstream. *Opt. Express* 2017, 25(6), 5951-5961.
- 441 12. Ye, F. et al. Simple analytical expression for crosstalk estimation in homogeneous trench-assisted multi-
442 core fibers. *Opt. Express* 2014, 22(19), 23007-23018.

- 443 13. Masanori, K. et al. Analytical expression of average power-coupling coefficients for estimating intercore
444 crosstalk in multicore fibers. *IEEE Photonics J.* 2012, 4(5), 1987-1995.
- 445 14. Zhou, J. A non-orthogonal coupled mode theory for super-modes inside multi-core fibers. *Opt. Express*
446 2014, 22(9), 10815-10824.
- 447 15. Diamandi, H. H.; London, Y.; Zadok, A. Opto-mechanical inter-core cross-talk in multi-core fibers. *Optica*
448 2017, 4(3), 289-297.
- 449 16. Koshiba, M. et al. Multi-core fiber design and analysis: coupled-mode theory and coupled-power theory.
450 *Opt. Express* 2011, 19(26), B102-B111.
- 451 17. Matsuo, S. Crosstalk behavior of cores in multi-core fiber under bent condition. *IEICE Electron. Express* 2011,
452 8(6), 385-390.
- 453 18. Hayashi, T. et al. Crosstalk variation of multi-core fibre due to fibre bend. *36th European Conference on*
454 *Optical Communications (ECOC) 2010*, Torino, Italy, paper We.8.F.6.
- 455 19. Fini, J. et al. Statistics of crosstalk in bent multicore fibers. *Opt. Express* 2010, 18(14), 15122-15129
- 456 20. Hayashi, T. et al. Design and fabrication of ultra-low crosstalk and low-loss multi-core fiber. *Opt. Express*
457 2011, 19(17), 16576-16592.
- 458 21. Chan, F. et al. Mode coupling dynamics and communication strategies for multi-core fiber systems. *Opt.*
459 *Express* 2012, 20(4), 4548-4563.
- 460 22. Chan, F.; Mudhana, G.; Lee, B. Influence of dissimilar cores on the mode-coupling dynamics of multicore
461 fibers. *IEEE Photon. Technol. Letters* 2012, 24(16), 1399-1401.
- 462 23. Fini, J. et al. Crosstalk in multicore fibers with randomness: gradual drift vs. short-length variations. *Opt.*
463 *Express* 2012, 20(2), 949-959.
- 464 24. Macho, A.; Morant, M.; Llorente, R. Experimental evaluation of nonlinear crosstalk in multi-core fiber. *Opt.*
465 *Express* 2015, 23(14), 18712-18718.
- 466 25. Sasaki, Y. et al. Single-mode 37-core fiber with a cladding diameter of 248 μm . *Optical Fiber Communication*
467 *Conference (OFC) 2017*, Los Angeles, US, paper Th1H.2.
- 468 26. Puttnam, B. J. et al. 2.15 Pb/s transmission using a 22 core homogeneous single-mode multi-core fiber and
469 wideband optical comb. *41st European Conference on Optical Communications (ECOC) 2015*, Valencia, Spain,
470 postdeadline pp.1-3.
- 471 27. Amma, Y. et al. High-density multicore fiber with heterogeneous core arrangement. *Optical Fiber*
472 *Communication Conference (OFC) 2015*, Los Angeles, US, paper Th4C.4.
- 473 28. Ryf, R. et al. 10-Mode Mode-Multiplexed Transmission over 125-km Single-Span Multimode Fiber. *41st*
474 *European Conference on Optical Communications (ECOC) 2015*, Valencia, Spain, postdeadline 1-3.
- 475 29. Sakaguchi, J. et al. Realizing a 36-core, 3-mode Fiber with 108 Spatial Channels. *Optical Fiber Communication*
476 *Conference (OFC) 2015*, Los Angeles, US, paper Th5C.2.
- 477 30. Doerr, C. R. Silicon photonics for space-division multiplexing. *IEEE Photonics Society Summer Topical*
478 *Meeting* 2012, 242-243.
- 479 31. Koonen, A. M. J.; Chen, H.-S.; van den Boom, H. P. A.; Raz, O. Silicon Photonic Integrated Mode
480 Multiplexer. *IEEE Photonics Society Summer Topical Meeting* 2012, 240-241.
- 481 32. Ding, Y.; Kamchevska, V.; Dalgaard, K.; Bacco, D.; Rottwitt, K.; Hu, H.; Galili, M.; Morioka, T.; Oxenløwe,
482 L. K. Silicon photonics for multicore fiber communication. *Asia Communications and Photonics Conference*
483 2016, paper AF1G.1.
- 484 33. Lindenmann, N. et al. Connecting Silicon Photonic Circuits to Multicore Fibers by Photonic Wire Bonding.
485 *IEEE J. Lightwave Technol.* 2016, 33(4), 755-760.
- 486 34. Samsung Electronics Co, "5G Vision", available at [http://www.samsung.com/global/business-](http://www.samsung.com/global/business-images/insights/2015/Samsung-5G-Vision-0.pdf)
487 [images/insights/2015/Samsung-5G-Vision-0.pdf](http://www.samsung.com/global/business-images/insights/2015/Samsung-5G-Vision-0.pdf), 2015.
- 488 35. Waterhouse, R.; Novak, D. Realizing 5G: Microwave Photonics for 5G Mobile Wireless Systems. *IEEE*
489 *Microw. Magazine* 2015, 16, 84-92.
- 490 36. Barrera, D.; Gasulla, I.; Sales, S. Multipoint two-dimensional curvature optical fiber sensor based on a non-
491 twisted homogeneous four-core fiber. *IEEE J. Lightwave Technol.* 2015, 33(12), 2445-2450.
- 492 37. Capmany, J. et al. Microwave photonic signal processing. *IEEE J. Lightwave Technol.* 2013, 31, 571-586.
- 493 38. Seeds, A. Microwave photonics. *IEEE Trans. Microwave Theory Tech.* 2002, 50(3), 877-887.
- 494 39. Capmany, J.; Novak, D. Microwave photonics combines two worlds. *Nat. Photonics* 2007, 1, 319-330.
- 495 40. Yao, J. Microwave photonics. *IEEE J. Lightwave Technol.* 2009, 27(3), 314-335.

- 496 41. Diamandi, H. H.; London, Y.; Zadok A. Opto-mechanical inter-core cross-talk in multi-core fibers. *Optica*
497 2017, 4, 289-297.
- 498 42. Yao, J. Microwave photonics. *IEEE J. Lightwave Technol.* 2009, 27, 314-335.
- 499 43. Wilner, K.; Van Den Heuvel A. P. Fiber-optic delay lines for microwave signal processing. *Proc. IEEE*, 1976,
500 64, 805-807.
- 501 44. Capmany, J. et al. New and flexible fiber-optic delay-line filters using chirped Bragg gratings and laser
502 arrays. *IEEE Trans. Microwave Theory Tech.* 1999, 47(7), 1321-1326.
- 503 45. Zeng, F.; Yao, J. All-optical microwave filters using uniform fiber Bragg gratings with identical
504 reflectivities. *IEEE J. Lightwave Technol.* 2005, 23(3), 1410-1418.
- 505 46. Wang, C.; Yao, J. Fiber Bragg gratings for microwave photonics subsystems. *Opt. Express* 2013, 21(19),
506 22868-22884.
- 507 47. Morton, P. A.; Khurgin, J. B. Microwave photonic delay line with separate tuning of the optical carrier.
508 *IEEE Photon. Technol. Lett* 2009, 21(22), 1686-1688.
- 509 48. Marpaung, D.; Roeloffzen, C.; Heideman, R.; Leinse, A.; Sales, S.; Capmany, J. Integrated microwave
510 photonics. *Lasers Photon. Rev.* 2013, 7(4), 506-538.
- 511 49. Sancho, J.; Bourderionnet, J.; Lloret, J.; Combríe, S.; Gasulla, I.; Xavier, S.; Sales, S.; Colman, P.; Lehoucq, G.;
512 Dolfi, D.; Capmany, J.; De Rossi, A. Integrable microwave filter based on a photonic crystal delay line. *Nat.*
513 *Communications* 2012, 3, 1075.
- 514 50. Ohman, F.; Yvind, K.; Mørk, J. Slow Light in a Semiconductor Waveguide for True-Time Delay
515 Applications in Microwave Photonics. *IEEE Photon. Technol. Letters* 2007, 19(15), 1145-1157.
- 516 51. Gasulla, I.; Capmany, J. Microwave photonics applications of multicore fibers. *IEEE Photonics J.* 2012, 4(3),
517 877-887.
- 518 52. Garcia, S.; Gasulla, I. Design of Heterogeneous Multicore Fibers as Sampled True-Time Delay Lines. *Opt.*
519 *Lett.* 2015, 40(4), 621-624.
- 520 53. Garcia, S.; Gasulla, I. Dispersion-engineered multicore fibers for distributed radiofrequency signal
521 processing. *Opt. Express* 2016, 24, 20641-20654.
- 522 54. Wang C.; Yao, J. Fiber Bragg gratings for microwave photonics subsystems. *Opt. Express* 2013, 21, 22868-
523 22884.
- 524 55. Birks, T. et al. Multicore optical fibres for astrophotonics. *CLEO/Europe and EQEC 2011 Conference Digest*,
525 Munich, Germany, paper JSIII2_1.
- 526 56. Gasulla, I.; Barrera, D.; Hervás, J. and Sales, S. Spatial Division Multiplexed Microwave Signal processing
527 by selective grating inscription in homogeneous multicore fibers. *Sci. Reports* 2017, no. 41727, 1-10.
- 528 57. Yao, X. S.; Maleki, L. Multiloop optoelectronic oscillator. *IEEE J. Quantum Electron.* 2000, 36(1), 79-84.
- 529 58. Bánky, T.; Horváth, B.; Bercei, T. Optimum configuration of multiloop optoelectronic oscillators. *J. Opt.*
530 *Soc. Am. B* 2006, 23(7), 1371-1380.
- 531 59. Garcia, S.; Gasulla, I. Multi-cavity optoelectronic oscillators using multicore fibers. *Opt. Express* 2015, 23(3),
532 2403-2415.
- 533 60. Li, W.; Yao, J. An optically tunable optoelectronic oscillator. *J. Lightwave Technol.* 2010, 28(18), 2640-2645.
- 534 61. Lelièvre, O. et al. Ultra-low phase noise 10 GHz dual loop optoelectronic oscillator. *Proceedings of IEEE 2016*
535 *Int. Topical Meeting on Microwave Photonics (IEEE, 2016)*, 106-109.
- 536 62. Yao, X. S.; Maleki, L. Optoelectronic microwave oscillator. *J. Opt. Soc. Am. B* 1996, 13(8), 1725-1735.
- 537 63. Garcia, S.; Gasulla, I. Experimental demonstration of multi-cavity optoelectronic oscillation over a
538 multicore fiber. *Opt. Express* 2017, 25(20), 23663-23668.
- 539

